

THE ISSUE OF SUPPLY OF ARTELS AND COOPERATIVES IN THE TERRITORIES OF THE UZBEK SSR

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Abstract: This paper describes the supervision of equipment safety in enterprises operating in the state craft co-operative system, where it is entrusted to the insurance funds of the craft co-operatives of the social security system. The paper also describes the Namangan Oblast Craft Insurance Fund, which was established in 1943 and the works performed in this area.

Keywords and phrases: craft cooperative, private property, insurance, technical safety, cooperative property, labour protection.

A cooperative social security system is known to have been formed in the territories of the Uzbek SSR in the 30s of the 20th century in handicraft co-operatives. Since then, the cooperative has been performing some social tasks in the society, such as providing pensions, creating conditions for their recreation and health improvement, organising summer camps for children and pre-school educational institutions. Although it was not characteristic of the social security system to supervise the safety of equipment in enterprises operating under the state craft co-operative system, the craft co-operative insurance funds were responsible for this. For instance, the Namangan Oblast Craft Insurance Fund was established in 1943, and by 1945 it had 45 artisan co-operatives under its control. The total number of insured people totalled 5,707. [1.369–375.]

The report of the Insurance and Mutual Aid Fund of Uzbekistan at the meeting of the Union of Insurance and Mutual Aid Funds (1946) stated: "...that the main direction of activity of the Insurance and Mutual Aid Funds is the issue of labour protection. The main task is to create the best conditions to protect workers and employees at work from injuries, despite the presence of a special inspection on labour protection and technical safety, in most cases there are cases of disorder in the production buildings of artels, unsatisfactory labour protection and technical safety at enterprises". Also at this meeting, "in the first 9 months of 1945, 21 fatalities occurred at the enterprises of the system, and in the first 9 months of 1946, 44 such cases were registered." It was pointed out that there was a situation of fatalities, especially among adolescents, and the reason was that they were not provided with the necessary conditions and were not allowed to work with the equipment without the technical instructions being explained to them. In fact, the information provided was deplorable for the time, although these problems were discussed at various meetings, but there was no significant change in practice.

In the letter of the Cash Union of Insurers and Mutual Aid of Uzbekistan dated 12 August 1947 the following information can be found: The total number of artels in the cooperative and handicraft cash desk of the Cash Union of Insurers and Mutual Aid of Uzbekistan is 388 and the total number of people working in them is 35,016, of whom 20,827

are men and 14,316 are women. In particular, 98 artels operate in the Andijan, Namangan and Ferghana provinces, with 10,510 insured persons and 357 pensioners [2.1].

In 1947 there were 369 bureaus for improvement of life and labour protection of artisanal workers, including 30 kindergartens, 21 nurseries, 44 medical stations. There were no recreation centres or pioneer camps.

According to the decision of the Presidium of the Association of Uzbekistan of 28 September 1948 on determining the amount of benefits for the period of temporary incapacity for work of the members of the artel (according to the decision of the Council of Ministers of the USSR on 9 August 1948) "To the disabled of Uzbekistan All members of the artel by the social insurance fund in all cases of incapacity for work, except maternity benefits, are paid the following amounts: when working in the same artel for more than 8 years - 100 per cent, up to 5-8 years - 80 per cent, up to 3-5 years - 60 per cent, up to 3 years - 50 per cent and for teenagers up to 18 years - 60 per cent [3.2].

According to the annual report of the "Socialism" artel in Ferghana for 1950, 29 members of the artel were provided with material support worth 6,480 soums during the year. In addition, the members of the artel were paid an extra 1,413 soums to send them to pioneer camps and holiday homes. The biggest assistance amounted to 2800 soums allocated to orphanage No.1, besides, foodstuffs were given during the year. 7376 soums were spent on repairing houses where members of the artel live.

According to the report on the work carried out by the Crafts Insurance Fund of Namangan region for the first half of 1948 to the second half of 1950, a number of changes were made in the field of labour protection and cultural and domestic affairs. There were 241 insurance assets working in artels, and 175 children of artel workers were brought up in kindergartens and kindergartens of the Crafts Insurance Fund of Namangan region. In 1950, in order to improve working conditions, a financial agreement was concluded with the management of the artels for all the artels and mutual aid boxes were established in them. These help boxes collected 150,800 soums and served 2,500 members [4.33].

When issuing referrals to artel members in all district craft insurance councils, 20 sanatoria, 64 rest homes for every thousand registered craft co-operatives and 44 sanatoria for disabled co-operatives, 91 norms for rest homes were established.

At the meeting of the craft council of Andijan province on 14 October 1953, the decision of the general meeting of the artel "Kizil Botir" of 10 October 1953 was considered, in which the death of the artel member U. Toshmatov's husband, it became clear that their four youngest children needed clothes and shoes, as well as financial support.

Another important aspect of co-operative ownership was that, unlike hired labourers, members participated in artel activities, received financial support, improved their living conditions, and were protected from various layoffs. Another important aspect of the issue was that the provision of benefits to artel workers was at the expense of the system's own funds. The pension was paid by the management of the artel at the expense of insurance premiums of the artel.

In conclusion, it can be said that the industrial artels, being not only an organisational and economic structure, also fulfilled the task of an organisation playing an important role in solving the social problems of its members. Especially in the post-war years, a number of activities were carried out in the field of employment, medical care, training in new professions, and social adaptation. The organisation of special artels for the disabled and the

use of homeworkers in conditions not devoid of organisational shortcomings and defects were seen as a unique solution to social problems for their time. Here, the articles provided material support at their own expense to restore the health of the disabled, purchase prostheses and special footwear.

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